

Achieving resilience in the hotel industry during COVID-19, is cutting out the intermediary the solution?

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ABSTRACT

Before the outbreak of COVID-19, the hotel sector was already pessimistic about the future, due to the impact of intermediary platforms for the booking process. High fees have to be paid and all hotel rooms were lumped together. With the outbreak of COVID-19, the situation has worsened because tourism in general has decreased and so have the revenues. This study looks at the sector through a lens of IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing, Business Process Integration and Cyber Security. These analyses draw a conclusion about the extent to which factors influence the decision for hotels to cut the intermediary out of the booking process, now that COVID-19 is putting pressure on cutting costs in order to survive this crisis.

Keywords

COVID-19, Hotel industry, Intermediary platforms, Digital transformation & Disruptive events

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is affecting almost all markets and sectors, ushering in a global health crisis, which has led to a devastating financial impact. Decisions had to be taken to close hotels, restaurants, cinemas, etc. caused by the disruptive effect the virus has on the travel ecosystem (Deloitte, 2020). Thus, the hospitality industry was one of the first sectors to experience this financial crisis through a major decrease in tourism.

The pandemic also has effects on online intermediary platforms, handling services such as the booking process for the hotels. For example, AirBnB has seen a decrease in short term rental reservations of 95% in week 14 of 2020, when compared to the same time in 2019 (Lock, 2020). Furthermore, Booking Holdings Inc. (better known as Booking.com), announced that they will be laying

off 25% of their employees (Bloomberg, 2020). This statement has come not too long after AirBnB and Tripadvisor announced similar employee lay off figures. Hotels work closely with such companies to create more value during the booking process for their customers.

The relationship between the two aforementioned actors is being tested by COVID-19. This research will focus on how the hotel industry can stay resilient throughout the crisis and survive the impact. In order to do so, the focus will be on the role that online intermediary platforms play within the hotel industry. Thus, a clear motive is presented to conduct research into the impact of the COVID-19 virus on the hotel industry and to provide advice to hotel chains on how to become more resilient and overcome this crisis.

The managerial relevance mainly comes from the advice, which will be given to the hotel industry in the conclusion and through the analysis conducted from a IT governance, business process and cyber security perspective. Throughout this research, several pieces of advice will be given on how the hotels have to adapt the way they conduct their business and IT in order to survive the impacts of this pandemic. Moreover, the research will provide an insight into the way forward for the hotel industry if the online intermediary platforms go bankrupt due to the effects of the crisis, as well as into the factors influencing the decision to use such platforms during and after the crisis if they survive financially.

The scientific relevance of this research is provided through an academic literature review, which will make several recommendations on both future researches to be conducted and the effects of disruptive events on the role of online intermediary platforms in the hotel industry. Furthermore, this research will generate general implications and academic knowledge on the influence of disruptive events on (dis) intermediation.

The above-mentioned impact on the hotel

industry and the online intermediary platforms provides the ground for this research and mandates its relevance both to management and science. Chapter 2 will provide a more in depth insight into the objectives, methodology and scope of the research.

RESEARCH RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The aim of this study is to clarify the influence of a disruptive event, like COVID-19, on the use of online intermediaries in the hotel industry. Since the emergence of intermediaries in the hotel industry, their popularity is continuously increasing (Romero & Tejada, 2020). However, little is known about what would happen if these intermediaries are forced to withdraw from the market as a consequence of a disruptive event, for example if Booking.com declared bankruptcy due to of COVID-19. As this pandemic is limiting the freedom to move around the world, this will impact both the demand for the hotel industry as well as the customers' decisions for travel destinations.

The scope of this research is on the role of intermediary platforms in the booking process of a hotel room. Did this role change during the pandemic? What will happen if Booking.com or comparable platforms go bankrupt? Is this the time to focus on your own IT structure as a hotel chain and become independent of intermediary platforms? Therefore, our research question is stated as follows:

“What is the effect of disruptive events, like COVID-19, on the use of intermediary platforms in the hotel industry, especially from the viewpoint of digital transformation?”

RESEARCH APPROACH

In case of a disruptive event, it is important to use timely data from primary sources, as this situation is unprecedented and therefore there is no 'correct' procedure in place to deal with such events. However, secondary literature, like academic journal articles, is necessary to substantiate the findings and to be able to make a prediction for the future. Therefore, both primary and secondary literature is used in this research. The primary data will be collected from recent articles, internal reports and interviews, while the secondary data is derived from academic literature. The collected literature will be analyzed based on specific relevant information for our research, which will be summarized in a table in order to give an overview of topic-related literature. Based on this literature, the role of intermediaries will be analyzed, and recommendations and predictions will be proposed in order to cope with disruptive events such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

The cases, which will be selected in the literature research, will include hotel actors of different sizes. Furthermore, in order to compare the impacts of a disruptive event on the hotel industry, the aim is to find both cases with and without parties that act as intermediaries for hotel services.

At the end, a conclusion will be drawn out of the analyzed cases and recommendations will be made. The aim is that this conclusion will be applicable to the overall hotel industry, and especially those actors that make use of an intermediary within that industry. In addition, the objective of the recommendations is to advise on the hotels' necessity for the use of intermediary agencies after COVID-19.

HOTEL INDUSTRY MARKET ANALYSIS

The global hotel industry is a \$525 billion industry, made up of over 18 million rooms (International Hotel Group, 2018). The tourism industry, under which the hotel industry is branched, is particularly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to travel restrictions and an overall decrease in demand, international tourism has decreased with 60%. If the crisis is not averted by December, this is expected to increase to 80% (OECD, 2020). Within this industry it has become common to utilize intermediary platforms for customer acquisition through booking offerings. If a company doesn't work with an intermediary, they risk losing exposure to customers (Lakshmi & Shareena). The market leaders within this industry are, amongst others; Booking.com, Expedia and AirBnB. Hotels without a company specific reservation platform gain value through the utilization of intermediary platforms services.

The hotel industry is thus closely related to the industry of the intermediary platforms in the hospitality industry. While the market for intermediary platforms can certainly offer massive values for hotels, the dissatisfaction regarding the platform's 'piece of the pie' has increased over the years (Zhang, Chen, Guo & Li, 2019). This is comparable to intermediary platforms within other industries like restaurants that deliver through platforms like Just Eat & Takeaway. Suppliers increasingly try to avoid the platforms, as their fee-percentages are increasing over the years and allow intermediary platforms to sometimes ask 30 to 35 per cent (Lakshmi & Shareena). Prior to COVID-19, 845 million room bookings were placed through websites owned by Booking Holdings (Booking Holding, 2020).

This is one of the main reasons why optimism amongst the industry's CEO's in the hotel sector was already low. This is measured in PwC's industry report (2020) through CEO confidence in the increase of revenue over 2020 The hotels are

required to pay high fees in order to be visible on these platforms, in 2019 alone large hotel chains lost 10-15% of their revenue as a result of commission paid to these platforms, for small chains or independent hotels this range is higher at: 18-22% (PwC, 2019). Even more devastating to the hotels is that their rooms are becoming a form commodity, as long as the reviews are positive across some platforms, customers do think that they can compare all rooms with the same ranking (PwC, 2019).

Furthermore, through the industry analysis conducted by PwC (2019) indicated that one of the main strategies for the hotel industry to compete with the intermediary platforms is to implement emerging technologies. Through this implementation, two major goals can be achieved. First, savings within the back-end administrative processes can be achieved through the integration of business processes through a BPI solution. Secondly, digital programs can be created in order to improve the perceived quality and convenience of the interactions between the hotel (chain) and its customers.

Thus, it can be concluded that the hotel industry was in need of drastic digital transformations in order to compete with the intermediary platforms and become independent resilient actors once again. This need is being accelerated due to the financial consequences of COVID-19 on the intermediary platforms (Lock, 2020; Bloomberg, 2020). If the third parties which a hotel relies on for the customer influx has to leave the market (due to bankruptcy for example), the hotel needs to be able to continue with their business processes as useful. This can only be achieved if the hotel industry can act independently of the intermediary platforms. Furthermore, research (Soto-Acosta, 2020) has shown that COVID-19 on its own serves as a digital transformation accelerator. Thus, our research will focus on the business process integration and IT governance and digital transformation strategies, which can assist the hotel industry to become independent of the intermediary platforms as well as becoming resilient to future disruptive events.

ANALYSIS

This chapter conducts analysis from the IT Governance, Business Process Integration and Cyber Security perspectives (in that order). This chapter as a whole will focus on conducting objective analysis from the aforementioned standpoints. Throughout chapter 4, no opinions or pieces of advice will be provided. The chapter will solely focus on conducting the analysis and providing an insight into the results without drawing conclusions. For each of the analyses, a baseline will

be provided prior to the results, in order to be able to draw objective conclusions in chapter 5.

IT GOVERNANCE AND STRATEGIC SOURCING

In order to properly address the influence of COVID-19 on IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing in the hotel industry, this research will address the following two aspects. First, the influence of COVID-19 on digital transformation in the hotel industry as a whole. Secondly, the influence of COVID-19 on the IT governance archetypes in the hotel industry. Both aspects will be addressed through a brief before and after COVID-19 analysis.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION BEFORE COVID-19

An industry study has shown that the hotel industry (prior to COVID-19) was being affected by the digital transformation, which was influencing the market since its emergence. Large intermediary platforms, such as Trip Advisor and booking.com, had a strong influence on the way the market was shaped and behaved in the last decade. For example, the commissions paid to third-party booking services amount up to 10 to 22 percent for hotels in 2019 (PwC, 2019). However, the major impact is based on the effect this has had on the way consumers decide on their booking decision. Since differentiation between competitors on such platforms is mainly perceived through price differences and quality has been outshone by consumer reviews and star ratings (PwC, 2019). Thus, the strategic advice offered by PwC to the market in 2019, was to modernize the service offering and implement the latest technology. Adding to this, PwC states that in 2019, hotels have underutilized the potential of new technologies to be implemented. The hotel industry has automated some of their back-office and administrative tasks, but solely to reduce the amount of employees and costs, hence not fully committing to a digital transformation.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION DURING COVID-19

Since COVID-19 has started to disrupt demand in and supply globally for all sectors, the hotel industry was hit as well. Primarily by a major decrease in tourism and thus demand, which has led to a decrease in international tourism of 60%. If the crisis is not averted by December, this is expected to increase to 80% (OECD, 2020). Soto-Acosta (2020), concluded that in order to combat the COVID-19 pandemic with resilience and avoid short-term financial collapse, companies are accelerating the adoption of digital transformation. Fully committing to digital transformation, not solely to cut costs but to gain a competitive advantage is the approach for

the hotel industry to become resilient once more. COVID-19 is thus serving as the accelerator and catalyst for digital transformation, influencing the IT Governance archetypes implemented by the hotel industry (more on this subject in chapter 4.1.3). As such, hotel chains have to create well-founded digital transformation strategies to guide the process of the transformation, which will focus on becoming resilient and independent from third actors for their demand. In order to create such a strategy and implement it accordingly, the C-level executives will have to work together on its creation. Whilst the COO and CIO will have the leadership roles, accounting for both the IT implications and the implications to the operations. This DT strategy is to aim towards a better alignment of the IT governance and technological possibilities to the financial governance, whilst optimizing the utilization of the key assets. In order to achieve the creation of such a DT strategy, the C-level executives should at least address the following aspects; Changes in value creation dimensions, use of technology, financial aspect dimensions & structural change dimensions (Ou & Alexiou, 2020). All four should be addressed both from the perspective of the influence which COVID-19 has had on the aspect as well as how to mitigate this effect or even how to use it to gain a competitive advantage. From an implementation standpoint (after the realization of the DT strategy), the hotel chain needs to establish management practices for the governance of the complex digital transformation. In order to achieve this, the before mentioned strategy needs to serve as a central concept which integrates the entire coordination, prioritization and implementation of the digital transformation across the firm (Matt, Hess & Benlian, 2015).

IT GOVERNANCE PRIOR TO AND DURING COVID-19

In order to make sure a well-founded understanding of the IT governance within the hotel industry is acquired. The tables (1 & 2) below show the governance matrix from before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Domain Archetype	IT Principles	IT Architecture	IT Infrastructure	Business Application Needs	IT Investment
Business Monarchy					
IT Monarchy		X			
Feudal					
Federal				X	
IT Duopoly	X		X		X
Anarchy					

Table 1. Governance Matrix (Ross & Weill, 2004) prior to COVID 19

Domain Archetype	IT Principles	IT Architecture	IT Infrastructure	Business Application Needs	IT Investment
Business Monarchy	X		X		X
IT Monarchy		X			
Feudal					
Federal					
IT Duopoly				X	
Anarchy					

Table 2. Governance Matrix (Ross & Weill, 2004) post COVID 19

During a crisis it is important to have consistent decision rights. Companies in the industry should thus experience a change in their IT governance structure. IT Principles need to be (re)defined to support the business during this period of global pandemic. Prior to COVID-19, the IT governance was usually managed through an IT Duopoly archetype. This assumption is based on the usefulness of a collaboration between IT and either an executive group or with business unit leaders in defining IT principles (Weill & Ross, 2004). Since COVID-19, a Business Monarchy should be overseeing the process of defining IT principles. This is crucial for a company to correctly use IT to suit current but rapidly changing business needs. Also, Carlson Companies uses a similar strategy in the travel industry as they went through a similar process in the past (Weill & Ross, 2004). Next, with some input from top managers, the IT Monarchy has to highlight the integration and standardization requirements. Here, there is no change in the archetype, since it is still viewed upon as a technical rather than a strategic step (Weill & Ross, 2004). Moreover, IT specialists can provide a list of shared and enabling services that fit the new role of IT. The involvement of the CIO in defining the principles and his or her role as IT architecture decision maker supports the centralized decision-making process during a crisis (Ou & Alexiou, 2020). Additionally, the shift from IT Duopoly to Business Monarchy for IT infrastructure is beneficial, since it provides clear instructions to IT specialists regarding the disruptively emerging strategy of the company. The Federal approach to business application needs changed as well. The IT perspective should be taken into account on a company wide instead of being limited to independent business units. Decisions should be based on current IT infrastructure capabilities and technical standards in order to select the correct applications to be implemented. Finally, regarding IT investments, it is of importance to correctly prioritize which business processes receive IT support. Due to the need for centralized decision making (Ou & Alexiou, 2020), IT investment decisions need to be made by business executives as a response to business priorities. During a crisis, this could mean the difference between survival and bankruptcy. A rapid change in environment causes existing IT governance models to shift. This shift is a major challenge for companies as it disrupts the

status quo of IT governance for the period to come. Thus, deriving from the findings above, the following governance matrix clearly indicates the change, which is taking place in the hotel industry's IT governance. The red X's indicate the situation prior to COVID-19, where the black X's indicate the current IT governance situation as a response to COVID-19.

Domain Archetype	IT Principles	IT Architecture	IT Infrastructure	Business Application Needs	IT Investment
Business Monarchy	X		X		X
IT Monarchy		X (no change)			
Feudal					
Federal				X	
IT Duopoly	X		X	X	X
Anarchy					

Table 3. Governance Matrix (Ross & Weill, 2004) change due to COVID-19

BUSINESS PROCESS INTEGRATION

This part of the assignment will be focused on the impact of COVID-19 on the Business Process Integration of the hotel industry. This is done by drawing two activity diagrams for a booking process of a customer at a hotel. One for the situation before COVID-19 and one for the situation after the outbreak of COVID-19. The changes are explained on the basis of three different aspects of change: regulations, adoption of new technologies and sub-processes.

CHANGES IN THE PROCESSES DUE TO REGULATION

The factor room capacity requires a new dimension due to the regulations on the COVID-19 pandemic. The number of households should be clear for the hotel in order to evaluate whether the customers are allowed to stay in the group composition they desire. So between the process where the customer states the room requirements and where the intermediary shows the available rooms, the group composition should be implemented. Furthermore, the payback policy according to the new rules and regulations regarding COVID-19 should be adapted and communicated to the customer. The intermediary should show these regulations to the customer, and the customer has to agree in order to book at the hotel.

Due to the pandemic, the hospitality branch is required based on regulations from the government to do an up-front check on whether the visitors had COVID-19 symptoms or were in contact with persons with COVID-19 symptoms (Rijksoverheid, n.d.). This causes a change in the booking process, which is visualized at the end of the post-COVID-19 activity diagram. Moreover, due to the differences in the circumstances of the COVID-19 crisis in different countries, travel advice

varies from country to country. This causes it to differ per traveler whether or not they are welcome in a country and therefore in a hotel. Before reserving a room for a customer, it is therefore first determined on the basis of the customer's address whether they are allowed to visit the country and thus book a room. This changed the booking process as can be seen in the post-COVID-19 activity diagram.

CHANGES IN THE PROCESSES DUE TO THE ADOPTION OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES

The hotel can decide to create its own platform in order to cut out the intermediary. This is not an explicit new technology; however, it can be new to privately use such a platform for the hotel. The intermediary platform would be replaced by a private booking platform, owned and controlled by the hotel (chain). COVID-19 may be a catalyst for hotels to be less dependent on intermediaries due to the uncertain hospitality-economy.

SUB PROCESSES THAT SHOULD BE CHANGED

Regulating and controlling guests is even more necessary than before, as an infected guest can cause major problems for the hotel, its personnel and customers. Due to this, extra checks should be conducted by the hotel to ensure that visitors are free of COVID-19. This can be done by asking the potential guest if he or she has any symptoms that could indicate a potential infection of COVID-19, one or two days prior to their arrival. Moreover, the adapted hotel policies should be communicated clearly to the customers in order to prepare them for the consequences of different scenarios while visiting the hotel. In addition, additional options to refund the amount paid must be added in case of cancellation due to circumstances related to COVID-19. This is a one-time adjustment in the booking agreement and therefore not visible in the activity diagram.

Below are the activity diagrams of the booking process, in both the pre- and post-COVID-19 situations. The changes in activity and process are shown in color in the post-COVID-19 diagram.

Figure 1. Activity Diagram Pre-COVID-19

Figure 2. Activity Diagram Post-COVID-19

WHAT IF AN INTERMEDIARY LEAVES THE MARKET DUE TO COVID-19

As can be seen in the activity diagram, the intermediary is playing a major role in the booking process of customers for a hotel. The lionshare of the activities flows through the intermediary, which obviously has its advantages and disadvantages. On one hand the hotel is dependent on the intermediary platform like Booking.com, who is also charging a percentage of the booking costs as a fee. One the

other hand, the hotel doesn't have to invest and maintain booking-platform software.

As a result of the corona crisis, the platforms such as Booking.com are under financial pressure because fewer rooms are booked due to the regulations on travelling. In august 2020, Booking.com showed their plans to cut off 25% of their employees as a result of the crisis (Bursztynsky, 2020). This shows that the corona crisis is having a huge negative impact on the company.

If Booking.com eventually goes bankrupt, it will have a lot of impact on hotels. Hotels will have to find another way to deal with their bookings. Moreover, the financial hassle it will produce might be something that hotels will try to avoid. So the decision on whether to wait and hope for stabilization of both the market and Booking.com or to take matters into their own hands and cut out the intermediary, is there to be made for hotels.

Opting for the latter means that hotels will have to invest and build their own platform for their website or switch to another (more stable) intermediary with a booking-platform. Besides the software development costs, additional complexities will stem from the fact that hotels still need to be visible and relevant for customers.

Although the COVID-19 crisis might be a catalyst to look for a way to be less dependent on booking platforms, the corona crisis will probably not change much in this process of becoming more independent. As cutting the intermediary out might lead to independence, it also provides hotels with a lot more uncertainty in already uncertain times.

CYBER SECURITY

Cyber-attacks on hotel chains are becoming increasingly common. Since 2010, several dozen big cyberattacks have been confirmed from large hotel chains (Kubacki, 2020). To date, the largest cyber-attack in the hotel sector took place in 2018 on the Marriot Hotel, with more than 383 million customer records stolen (Clement, 2020). As a result, this attack on the Marriot Hotel is ranked 12th in the world's largest cyber-attacks. For the hotel sector, this is a dangerous development, as they have to deal with large amounts of sensitive information, such as passports and credit card details, on a daily basis.

Since the rise of the COVID-19 pandemic,

almost every country in the world went into lockdown and the daily life as we used to know had changed completely (Dunford, Dale, Stylianou, Lowther, Ahmed, & Arenas, 2020). During the lockdown, citizens' interest in local events and news rose, because the situation and measures even varied from one region to another (Waugh, 2020). Cyber criminals, who were able to take advantage of the worldwide uncertainty, rapidly responded to this. The Microsoft Threat Protection Intelligence Team (2020) were able to prove this with their research as they discovered a large correlation between cyber attacks and local interests and news. Moreover, as employees immediately had to work from home, they often had to use their own computer, without knowing how to make a secure connection to the company network (Wolters, 2020). Only less than half have installed antivirus software or a firewall, which put the company's data at risk and created new opportunities for cybercriminals. As a result, Microsoft states that during COVID-19, between 20 000 and 30 000 phishing and other cyber attacks occur daily in the US alone (Microsoft Threat Protection Intelligence Team, 2020). Moreover, the founder of MonsterCloud and cyber-terrorism expert Zohar Pinhasi reports that during the pandemic, ransomware attacks increased by 800% (Waugh, 2020).

In the hotel sector, COVID-19 has also left its mark and opened the way for an increased risk of cyberattacks on hotels. Since many hotel staff had to work from home, cybercriminals could take advantage of the fact that they were easier distracted by roommates, children and pets (Escobar, 2020). This reduced the compliance of the basic safety rules more quickly, which reduced the awareness and detection of cyber attacks and made it possible for criminals to get away with it more often. Moreover, it is thought to be a calmer period for hotel staff, however, they receive far more emails than usual with questions regarding uncertainty about reservations, COVID-19 measures and restitutions (Short, 2020).

In order to tackle the influence of COVID-19 on Cyber Security and Risk Management in the hotel industry properly, this research focuses on the following four aspects. First, the potential cyber-security risks of the digital transformation in the hotel sector, as a result of COVID-19, will be identified. Then a risk analysis will be done and the results will be graphically presented in a risk matrix. Thereafter, security measures and controls will be proposed to mitigate the risk of cyber attacks. Finally, a conclusion will be drawn as to whether the remaining risk is acceptable.

POSSIBLE CYBER-SECURITY RISKS OF THE

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE HOTEL SECTOR

In a cyber attack, cyber criminals can exploit hotels' vulnerabilities for malicious activities. ICT components and software/applications are vulnerable if they are not up-to-date or used on unprotected devices (ABN AMRO, 2020). Because if systems or devices are not properly secured, they are at great risk of being used by cyber criminals to get into the company's network or to steal information. It is essential that all systems are provided with the latest software and security patches (Singer & Friedman, 2014). However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a sudden and enormous increase in working from home, making it more common for employees to work on personal devices (Escobar, 2020). Especially these 'vulnerable' devices are now a major cyber risk for hotels. For example, a weak password access management system or using the same password for different systems can increase the risk of the vulnerability of a system. When a cybercriminal, for example by phishing, has obtained the password, the criminal can get into any system and/or network where the same password is used (ABN AMRO, 2020; Singer & Friedman, 2014). In this way, cyber criminals have access and control over all the confidential hotel and guests information of those systems and networks. In this paper, the most common cybersecurity attacks on hotels, according to ABN AMRO (2020), Escobar (2020), Nayak (2020), and Singer and Friedman (2014), are used. Therefore, the possible cybersecurity risks for hotels are described below:

Phishing attacks: In recent years, this strategy has become more sophisticated. Phishing occurs most often by clicking on malicious links or attachments in emails (ABN AMRO, 2019). Opening a malicious link in an email can attempt to obtain login details or infect the hotel's computer with malware (Singer & Friedman, 2014). Clicking a malicious attachment in an email will automatically download malware in addition to the attachment, allowing cyber criminals to access the hotel network. An example of phishing is business email compromise, in which cybercriminals carefully target important people in the hotel, for example the CFO, CEO or financial department employees. They forge the e-mail address of the selected target by, for example, adding a single letter (Singer & Friedman, 2014). This is often not (directly) visible to the victimized employee. Subsequently, using the forged email address, the criminals try to mislead the employee into transferring money to the company. The result can be a large financial loss for a company (ABN AMRO, 2020). Moreover, the amount transferred is

often difficult to recover because the victim has executed a 'legitimate' transaction.

DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attacks: These network attacks focus on the capacity limit of the hotel's network resources, like the infrastructure of the hotel's website. In the event of a (D)DoS attack, large amounts of traffic are directed to the website. As a result, the website of the hotel can no longer function (properly) and becomes useless (Singer & Friedman, 2014).

Malware: There are two types of malicious software that are common in the hotel sector, ransomware and spyware. With ransomware, files in the computer become encrypted so that they can no longer be used by the hotel (ABN AMRO, 2020). These files can be decrypted only by transferring money to the criminals. When the money has been received, the documents may be released for use or get the decryption key to the decrypt files (Singer & Friedman, 2014). With spyware, Spyware collects data from a computer (or other device) and forwards it to cyber criminals (ABN AMRO, 2020). This is not visible to the hotel itself, which makes it even more risky for hotels, as it mainly involves confidential data such as usernames, passwords and payment details of the customers. An example of the combination of these two kinds of malware is DarkHotel Hacking, in which hotel's Wi-Fi can be used to target business guests during their visit. In this case, cybercriminals use falsified digital certificates to convince (important) guests that download software is safe to access, while in the meantime hacking their devices (Nayak, 2016). Another example is Point-of-Sales attacks, in which the payment system of hotels is attacked by cybercriminals, which could lead to payment card data breaches (ABN AMRO, 2020).

Third-party attack: It is the third party itself who abuses their relationship with the hotel. Weak security at contracted third parties, e.g. booking.com, or at external locations can be exploited by cybercriminals to gain unauthorized access to systems and thus confidential information (ABN AMRO, 2020; Singer & Friedman, 2014). Confidential information of the hotel or its customers, like credit card details, can be stolen and used for extortion or sale to other cyber criminals.

Insider threats: Insiders are persons within the hotel with access to its network information. Insiders are one of the biggest threats to hotels, because they often are part of an in-crowd. Insider threats in a hotel can take the form of sabotage, fraud, theft of assets, disturbance, espionage or stealing of intellectual property (Singer & Friedman,

2014). An insider threat can take place by a dissatisfied employee, a external contractor or someone with direct access to the building or host workstations of a company (ABN AMRO, 2020).

RISK ANALYSIS OF POTENTIAL CYBER SECURITY RISKS IN THE HOTEL SECTOR

Using the overview of potential cyber security risks in the hotel sector, two analyses are made. The first assesses the cyber risks in the CIA(A) triad, followed by a qualitative risk analysis which is conducted by assessing the probability of a cyber risk against its impact. The CIA(A) triad emphasizes the balance between confidentiality, integrity, availability and auditability of personal data in databases (Olivier, 2002). This balance has to consider the sensitivity of the data being stored and strive to maximize all three dimensions. According to Olivier (2002), confidentiality is intended to keep sensitive information protected and secret, for instance credit card data and passport data. In addition, integrity is about maintaining the reliability, accuracy and consistency of data. When files are modified during a cyber attack, data can for example be sabotaged or systems can be destroyed. Moreover, availability is the guarantee of reliable access to sensitive data by authorized users. This is for example affected during a DDoS attack, in which systems are inaccessible for an indefinite period of time. Furthermore, auditability is the assurance that all critical transactions' evidence has been stored in a reliable format for verification purposes. In this way, companies are able to track actions and events back to users, systems or processes that have been executed, to determine who is responsible for actions or omissions. Table 4 shows which dimensions of the CIA(A) triad are affected for each of the potential cyber risks (Olivier, 2002).

Table 4. CIA(A) Triad potential cyber risk for hotels

	Confidentiality	Integrity	Availability	Auditability
Vulnerability exploitation	X	X	X	X
Phishing	X	X		X
DDoS			X	
Malware	X		X	
Third party	X	X		
Insider threat	X	X		X

The second analysis is fully based on assumptions and logical reasoning. However, it is considered that this analysis applies to the situation for hotels before and after COVID-19, because research has shown that during the COVID-19 pandemic, no new types of cyber threats in the hotel sector were detected, however, the overall likelihood of a cyber attack increased (Deloitte,

2020; Escobar, 2020). Nevertheless, the situation before and after COVID-19 is not approached separately in a risk matrix, because the likelihood increases every year, but the probability of a cyber attack currently, as in 2019, still rises at a continuous level. As hotels hold large amounts of confidential data from both the hotel and its guests, the impact of data breaches in the hotel sector can be enormous. Take for example, the cyber attack on the Marriott hotel at the end of 2018, in which more than 500 million confidential customer files had been stolen (Fruhlinger, 2020). As a result of this data breach, the company's shares plummeted, they suffered reputation damage and were fined over \$120 million for violating guest privacy in the GDPR. Taking this all into account, the risk matrix (Ristić, 2013) of the potential cyber risks for hotels is as shown below:

Table 5. CIA(A) Triad potential cyber risk for hotels

POSSIBLE MEASURES AND CONTROLS TO MITIGATE THE RISKS

Table	x	Impact		
		Slightly harmful	Harmful	Extremely harmful
Likelihood	Likely	1	3	5
	Unlikely		4	2
	Highly unlikely			

As described above, there are many potential cyber attacks. Especially in times of COVID-19, when the turbulent times create great uncertainties and changes in all facets of life. The likelihood of these cyber attacks and their impact can be enormous. Therefore, it is crucial for hotels to protect themselves and prevent their systems to get attacked in the best possible way. Especially now that there are fewer guests in the hotels because of COVID-19, it is the ultimate time to train employees in cyber security (Deloitte, 2020). In this way, awareness is created, which helps them to better recognize cyber attacks, and to know which steps to take at such times. However, there are many different types of cyber attacks in the hotel sector, each of which needs to be approached and prevented in a different way. Therefore, it is important for the hotel sector to know the corresponding measures for each type of the potential cyber attacks mentioned above. Moreover, even though business email compromise can be scaled as 'phishing', it still needs specific measures to reduce the risk, therefore, it is included in table 5 as illustrated on the next page.

To maximize the protection of the CIA(A)-triad dimensions, some additional measures have to be taken into account (Olivier, 2002). To improve confidentiality, data encryption and two-factor authentication can make a major contribution. Moreover, integrity can be strengthened by making backups of important files and systems, so that unauthorized adjustments can be detected and adjusted back to the original version. Furthermore,

the availability of systems can be enhanced by the usage of proper firewalls and proxy servers to guard against DDoS attacks. In addition, the auditability can be strengthened by an internal audit log to monitor who accesses which files (Singer and Friedman, 2014) and external IT audit checks (Wolters, 2020).

Therefore, additional measures need to be taken to ensure greater protection against cyber threats than competitors do, especially in times of the above-mentioned increased cyber risk during COVID-19. In this way, the hotel will be less attractive to cybercriminals, which will reduce the likelihood of an attack. That is why the first step in upgrading cybersecurity will be enhancing vulnerability protection, to prevent cyber attacks from being successful. Then, as shown in the risk matrix, the biggest priority for hotels is to prevent DDoS, malware and insider threat. Hence, protection measures against third parties, such as Booking.com, and phishing attacks will, for now, be of decreased priority. Any measure taken to protect against cyber attacks reduces the likelihood of success, so the more measures taken the better. However, cyber criminals continue to innovate and look for new possible ways to attack, which is why constantly enhancing cyber security remains one of the most important tasks within hotels. Therefore, in order to combat the incessant cyber risk during COVID-19, hotels should at all times try to make their cyber-security outperform the competitors'.

Risk	Possible measures
Vulnerability exploitation	<p>Provide a proper vulnerability scanner, which scans software, computer systems and the hotel network components for vulnerabilities, like misconfiguration and outdated software (Singer & Friedman, 2014).</p> <p>Assign an IT specialist responsible for checking and identifying new vulnerability, and even more importantly making sure these vulnerabilities are fixed before cyber criminals can attack (ABN AMRO, 2020)</p> <p>A 'safebox' and an authorized environment, in which employees can retrieve and edit confidential information in a secure environment, can provide additional risk mitigation in times of COVID-19 (Hulstijn, 2020). This can be accomplished by using data encryption in a PKI and the use of secure VPN networks to access secret hotel data.</p> <p>Use a password manager, which can save all usernames and passwords used for all hotel networks and systems (Singer & Friedman, 2014; Wolters, 2020). This enables the usage of more complex passwords, in which punctuation marks, ciphers and capital letters can be utilized (ABN AMRO, 2020).</p>
Phishing	<p>Use good anti-virus software and spam protection, so that false emails can be blocked (ABN AMRO, 2020)</p> <p>Training focussed on recognizing phishing emails so that employees learn to check who sent the email beforehand and whether the content matches up to what that person would normally send (Deloitte, 2020)</p> <p>Designate a central phishing hotline to which suspicious emails can be reported and immediate action can be taken against in case of a phishing attack, which may limit the impact of the attack (Singer & Friedman, 2014).</p>
Business email compromise	<p>Use a good detection system, business email compromise can quickly be detected and emails which are not on the whitelist can be blocked (ABN AMRO, 2020).</p> <p>Establish hotel-wide rules for the use of the detection system of spoofed emails, employees can be alerted quickly and the potential impact of this attack can be lowered (Singer & Friedman, 2014).</p> <p>Frequently check blocked emails, emails that resemble the CEO or employee can be put on the blacklist by domain or sender. In this way, the detection system can work on its best and the likelihood and impact of a business email compromise can be minimized.</p>
DDoS	<p>Separate the hotel website from the employee network (ABN AMRO, 2020)</p> <p>Provide the web servers of the website with a Web Application Firewall (ABN AMRO, 2020)</p> <p>Segment the network, so that computers are unable to communicate with each other (Douligeris & Mitrokotsa, 2004).</p> <p>Use reputable suppliers which offer DDoS protection services, so that they can help to prevent and protect the hotel from DDoS attacks.</p>
Malware	<p>Create awareness among employees (Singer & Friedman, 2014). If they realise they must always check the sender's email address first and make sure that the content matches the sender, they will be less likely to make the mistake of responding to malware attacks (Nayak, 2016).</p> <p>Using good antivirus software can block most of the malware attacks beforehand (ABN AMRO, 2020).</p>
Insider threat	<p>Limit the employees' access to files and data to only the necessary.</p> <p>Limit the ability of unauthorized employees to read and edit important documents, as this prevents unauthorized employees from modifying files and granting themselves access to documents to which they have no rights (ABN AMRO, 2020).</p> <p>Maintain an audit log to monitor who viewed and edited which files (Singer & Friedman, 2014).</p> <p>Use external IT audit checks to make sure former employees no longer have access to the hotels' network and systems (Wolters, 2020)</p>
Third party attack	<p>Only use trusted parties.</p> <p>Create a clear service-level agreement about confidentiality, integrity and availability, and potential consequences (ABN AMRO, 2020).</p> <p>Assess the security audit of the third party and request proof of certificates, to make sure that their security is also at the desired level (Singer & Friedman, 2014).</p>

Table 6. Cyber risk matrix**DISCUSSION**

Throughout this chapter, discussion will be raised on the success factors and barriers as well as the short- and long-term implications on the hotel industry. Each of the topics will be discussed from the viewpoint of the analysis conducted in chapter 4; IT governance, Business Process Integration and Cyber Risk Management.

SUCCESS FACTORS AND BARRIERS

With regard to digital governance, the hotel industry has had its fair share of digital disruption with the emergence of intermediary platforms. Booking over the internet has become the preferred procedure by customers, mainly due to the option of easily comparing prices and quality related aspects. Through the emergence of the intermediary platforms, many hotels within the industry have become dependent on the flow of customers provided by such third parties. However, in order to overcome this dependency, become resilient and decrease the fee paid to third parties, hotels throughout the industry are to adapt and change their IT Governance. Especially during a crisis which leaves its marks on the financial position of the hotel industry, such third parties fairs and become critical.

Moreover, risk increases as more third parties are involved, therefore cutting out the intermediaries can reduce the cyberrisk of third-party attacks. However, there are other cyber risks with higher risks and likelihood, so due to a limited cybersecurity budget, those more 'dangerous' risks have priority when it comes to prevention.

Thus, in order to achieve a successful digital transformation, business processes are to be integrated and require the support of the decision-making structures. Moreover, hotels have to develop an IT strategy to be implemented throughout the hotel (chain) and its processes and procedures. Moving to a business monarchy is a solution applicable to most domains within the hotel industry.

This forces the hotels to align the business needs with the IT strategy and capabilities in order to become resilient. A link to the financial position and size of your hotel has to be made. If you only have a small hotel, with for example 4 rooms, chances are that you can handle it without a middleman, because word-of-mouth advertising will cover most of the bookings for the hotel. If you are in the middle class; large hotel, but not connected to a chain you will need more promotion to promote your hotel. If you are part of a hotel chain that is well known, the brand image will cause more recognition by potential customers, and thus a high probability

of more bookings.

Concluding, hotels should consider the option of running the operations independently of the intermediary platforms. There are several factors that are of great importance in deciding whether you can cut out the intermediary or not. To be able to do so, you need to make sure that you have created enough brand awareness among your customers, so that they will still find your hotel once searching for a place to stay. Connected to this is your customer loyalty. If high, this betters your position to do business on your own with the middleman. If low, the middleman can't be cut out as this will have too much impact on your number of bookings.

SHORT-TERM AND LONG-TERM IMPLICATIONS

From an IT governance perspective, the COVID-19 crisis and the decision to cut out the intermediary platforms have several short- and long-term implications. For the short term, in order to survive the current COVID-19 crisis and the financial consequences imposed by the virus, hotels will consider developing an IT strategy and corresponding IT governance to cut out the intermediary platforms. In doing so, the IT governance for the short term, will mostly be transformed to that of a business monarchy. This will align the IT strategy and competencies to the business requirements. Through this strategy, the intermediaries can be excluded from the business processes over time. Since this is a transformation which is not achieved overnight, it is likely that hotels will utilize the services of intermediaries until the process of transformation is complete.

For the long term, it is expected that hotels will create a robust IT strategy which enables them to attract sufficient numbers of customers without the assistance of intermediaries. The business monarchy governance is expected to be widely implemented for at least as long as the financial consequences last. Through this governance, the business requirements can be closely aligned with the IT strategy. Thus, making the hotel industry more competitive, agile and able to quickly adapt to changing IT opportunities in order to prevent new intermediary platforms from emerging and disrupting the hotel industry once more. The return of more stable and predictable times after the crisis could lead to a decrease in use of a business monarchy. Business needs crucial for survival during a crisis will be less relevant and other IT and business needs can be prioritized again.

From a business process integration perspective, the uncertainty of the future of the intermediary plays a major role in the implications on the short-term. As the hotel does not want to risk the hassle it brings when the intermediary would go bankrupt, hotels choosing to cut out an intermediary

may also be viewed as hotels betting on the bankruptcy of the intermediary. If the intermediary eventually goes bankrupt, hotels have the advantage to act as a 'first mover' and take a lionshare of the market share that intermediaries leave up to grab.

Cutting the intermediary is, on the short term, not a priority to the cyber security department of hotels. However, if the likelihood and risk of third parties increases significantly in the future, or if an additional budget is available, cutting the middleman will be a good idea on the longer term. This is because each third party involved increases the likelihood of a third party attack, which should be eliminated as best as possible.

Nevertheless, if the intermediary 'survives', hotels will have to compete with their previous platform suppliers for the long-term. This may not be a problem once a sufficient strategy is applied to stay relevant and appealing to potential customers. However, it may be difficult to compete with large third parties if financial resources are not in abundance. The model in which customers are asked about their COVID-19 symptoms only applies for the time COVID-19 is active, which probably will be relatively short-term. As this is not a major change in the pre-COVID-19 model, results from this change will not be significantly impacting the platform.

Overall, the implications for the short- and long-term results are dependent on the continuity of the intermediaries. Furthermore, it is a mitigation of different kinds of risks. Hotels either develop their own platform and take the risk of it having to compete with a surviving intermediary or they stay loyal to the intermediary and take the risk of the intermediary going bankrupt, after which they either have to switch to another (surviving) intermediary or develop their own platform after all.

CONCLUSION

The COVID-19 pandemic impacts the whole industry. The industry overall has suffered a catastrophic loss regarding the booking quantities. An example herein is the Hilton chain, which has suffered a reduction of 81% in their bookings (Marketwatch, 2020). Overall, the international tourism industry has seen their activity in bookings decline by 60% until now, and it is expected to decline by 80% by December (PwC, 2019).

Within the hotel industry, focus has been put on the role of the intermediary. Platforms used by these intermediaries are used for hotel bookings and allow hotels to be found online without creating an own platform or even an own website. Nevertheless, the impactful role of the

intermediaries results in hotels being dependent on their platforms, which logically costs the hotels in intermediary fees. With the uncertain times that the COVID-19 pandemic brings, the role and even more the dependence of IT has changed for hotels. As discussed, opting to cut out the intermediary will result in the necessity of a well-functioning IT department that can set up a private booking platform. Moreover, as COVID-19 can be seen as a catalyst for the overall digital transformation the world is going through, the importance of IT is increasing as a basic fundamental occurrence.

Travel restrictions being issued are not in the control of hotels. Thus, they need to focus on what they can influence. Exposure to customers, especially for local travel is crucial. The demand is smaller than before the crisis so capturing customer interest has become harder and competition is tougher. Thus, we recommend increasing online exposure and increasing the online experience for possible clients by developing or optimizing an online platform. This should be part of the digital transformation strategy. The efficiency of this strategy depends on hotel characteristics such as size and financial capability and therefore is not advisable to smaller businesses or businesses with financial troubles.

As COVID-19 still dominates large parts of the world and its long-term consequences are not yet known, more research will have to be done on this later, once academic literature on this subject becomes available. In addition, only short-term information is now available on the influence of COVID-19 on the hotel sector, over the long-term assumptions are now mainly made. Therefore, we recommend an in-depth study specifically on the influence of COVID-19 hotels (using booking intermediaries) might be interesting to investigate in the future.

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APPENDIX

Figure 1. Activity Diagram Pre-COVID-19

Figure 2. Activity Diagram Post-COVID-19

